

**"Nothing learned!" The media-ethical discourse on the visual coverage of the 2020
terror attack in Vienna**

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"Nothing learned!" The media-ethical discourse on the visual coverage of the 2020 terror attack in Vienna

Abstract

On November 2, 2020, Vienna, Austria, was hit by a terrorist attack. Countless photos and videos created by eyewitnesses were shared on social media and picked up by journalistic media. Especially the use of the images by two major Austrian media caused public outcry and an intensive media-ethical debate. This paper focuses on the meta-journalistic discourse on visual communication norms spurred by the visual media coverage of the attack, what was criticized and by whom, and the consequences of the discourse. A variety of actors spoke out, accusing the two media outlets of showing attack images that violate journalistic codes.

While there was a broad consensus that showing the images was inappropriate in the journalistic context, the level of reflection was generally low. The discussion was limited to image motives, but their aesthetics and modes of representation were not discussed. Thus, *how* something is depicted and what implications these depictions have was not adequately addressed.

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"Nothing learned!" The media-ethical discourse on the visual coverage of the 2020 terror attack in Vienna

On the evening of November 2, 2020, an armed man opened fire on people in a well-attended popular nightlife area in the city center of Vienna, Austria, killing four and injuring 23 people. The terrorist act lasted only nine minutes; then, the perpetrator was killed in an exchange of fire with police. However, since it was initially unclear whether it was a lone perpetrator, the city center was cordoned off; visitors to downtown Vienna had to retreat to pubs and hotels for several hours. For many hours, there was uncertainty about the dangerousness of the situation, rumors and eyewitness reports circulated on social media, and the Austrian media reported continuously in live special broadcasts and reports—although the state of knowledge remained vague.

This terrorist attack and its media coverage are of utmost interest to visual communication researchers because of the journalistic coverage, the amateur videos that quickly circulated on social media, and the counter-strategies of many users that were also based on visual communication. For example, countless photos and videos created by eyewitnesses in the city center were shared on social media and picked up by journalistic media. This means that user-generated live footage via social media has found its way into the coverage of Austrian media. This form of live journalism is made under high time pressure (Riegert & Olsson, 2007) and is characterized by speed (Bernhardt & Liebhart, 2019; Beuthner, 2003). Live, real-time reporting enhances the experiential nature and perceived authenticity, but at the same time, increases the risk of disseminating potential misinformation or disinformation, as well as ethically questionable material (Marthoz et al., 2017). One difficulty of live journalism is the journalistic evaluation of image material created outside the journalistic system with its norms and professional photojournalistic criteria (Isermann, 2015; Rauchfleisch et al., 2017). In these high-pressure live situations,

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where the assassination is often still ongoing, journalists must evaluate the accuracy and veracity of the material on the one hand. On the other, they have to determine if the material is from an ethical point of view acceptable to the audience or violates the rights of the persons depicted (Ghersetti & Johannson, 2021).

Communication and media studies, and visual communication research, in particular, can now draw on a vast body of knowledge on visual terror reporting and its consequences and problematics. For example, Marthoz et al. (2017), Müller and Knieper (2019), and Bernhardt (2016) demonstrate that visuals are used as a strategic tool to create visibility for terror. For this reason, it is essential to reflect closely on the use of visual motifs and aesthetics in reporting on terror as a main goal of terrorist attacks is to spread fear and terror. Constant repetition and sharing of fear-inducing, dramatic images in the news or social media reinforces this strategic goal (Christensen, 2017) and can attract copycats (Lankford & Madfis, 2018).

"Pictures of traumatic events, such as terrorist attacks, (...), seem able to capture the unimaginable. This is why news coverage of such traumas is frequently accompanied by images, as if they could provide audiences with a type of emotional insight that words cannot convey. Images seem to express the pain and distress of victims better than words do." (Bleiker, 2018, p. 9)

In this context, the traumatizing potential of images should not be underestimated. For example, when relatives learn of the injury or even killing of their loved ones through media images. But images can potentially traumatize every onlooker, in particular children. Visuals of terror usually capture and convey strong emotions and affects and are capable of evoking equally harrowing and distressing emotions in the viewers (Hutchison, 2018). Moreover, terror images often violate the human dignity of the depicted victims (Christensen, 2017; Marthoz et al., 2017; Müller & Knieper, 2019). In addition, media should preserve the human

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dignity of mourners and should use dignified forms of visual commemoration. Showing the perpetrators, in turn, gives them visibility and prominence and is suspected of having contagious effects on copycats (Beckett, 2016; Lankford & Madfis, 2018; Parker et al., 2019). In addition, the media can distort public opinion by reinforcing the perceived threat of terrorism posed by certain groups that could be blamed for the attack while downplaying the perceived threat posed by other potentially violent groups in the population (Laido et al., 2020). And finally, visual reports of the crime scene or the course of events can hinder police investigations (Bernhardt & Liebhart, 2019; Marthoz et al., 2017).

For this reason, several initiatives have published handbooks, guidelines, and recommendations for journalists on responsible terrorism or mass shooting coverage. Examples are the UNESCO "terrorism and the media" handbook (Marthoz et al., 2017) that highlights several examples of ethical dilemmas in terrorism coverage, the white papers on terrorism coverage by the Tow Center for Digital Journalism at the Columbia Graduate School (Beckett, 2016), and the "recommendations for reporting on mass shootings" (SAVE, 2017).

However, as Lim points out, in today's networked media landscape, images of (and by) terrorists "brought journalistic ethics and credibility to the forefront of the news media's contemporary role" (2016, p. 250, as cited in Mortensen, 2018, p. 1959), which, as Mortensen (2018) adds, put media self-censorship at the top of agenda. On the one side, self-censorship, so Mortensen, can protect the public from glorification and promotion of terrorist agendas. Still, on the other side, it engenders the risks of "suppressing reality and undermining the press' responsibility to inform the public" (p. 1958). She concludes that "neither media practitioners nor scholarship in the field seems to have found viable solutions to the dilemma of self-censorship" (p. 1966). But the evidence above shows that what Mortensen (2018) frames as "self-censorship" is an essential factor in ethically responsible terrorism reporting.

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For example, the experiment of Laido et al. (2020) shows that media coverage of terrorist attacks by Islamist terrorists that do not follow recommendations for responsible reporting (showing portraits of the perpetrator and disclosing personal information such as their name, age and that they were assumed to be Muslim) "appears to increase islamophobia" (Laido et al., 2020).

As this introduction shows, visual coverage of terror involves many trade-offs, balancing the public's interest against the dignity and personal protection of victims and their relatives, taking into account the possible traumatization of the viewers while keeping the top priority of not playing into the hands of terrorists' strategies.

Often, media coverage does not meet these requirements, which the example of the Vienna attack also showed. There were many problematic cases of visual communication that drew strong criticism. The self-control body of the Austrian press, the Austrian Press Council, received more than 1,500 complaints about the news coverage ("Over 1,500 complaints about reports on terrorist attack in Vienna"¹, 2020). The main reason for the complaints was the publication of amateur videos and pictures or footage from surveillance cameras showing a victim being shot or a policeman being gunned down. The complaints mainly concerned the media groups *Mediengruppe Österreich* and *Kronen Zeitung* with the corresponding tabloid media *OE24* (daily newspaper) and *oe24.at* (online news site) and *Kronen Zeitung* (daily newspaper) and *krone.at* (online news site).

This article does not aim to define what problematic, morally reprehensible, or bad journalistic practice is. The Austrian Press Council has already explained this in detail in its multi-page decisions and media ethics assessments (Österreichischer Presserat, 2021: Decisions 2020/306, 2020/295, 2020/301 and 2020/293). Violations of the Code of Ethics of the Austrian Press were found in several cases: they mainly concerned severe violations of

¹ When we quote titles or content from reporting, we use the English translations.

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"protection of personality" and "privacy." The following list gives an overview of the detected violations concerning image contents. Even though the verbal description of this emotionalizing and potentially traumatizing content does not suffice to provide "the whole picture" of the event, we refrain from showing the images in this article for ethical reasons, as it is neither objectively justified nor purposeful to do so (franzke et al., 2020).

These violations of the code of ethics occurred through

- publication of videos depicting the shooting of a passer-by,
- publishing a video showing a shot police officer going to ground,
- publication of an unpixellated photo depicting two fleeing women,
- publication of an unpixellated photo depicting the body of the shot assassin,
- publication of a photo showing the body of an injured man with bloodstained trousers (who was identifiable despite the picture being taken from behind),
- publication of a photo showing a traumatized woman lying on the floor with an injured foot (among other things, due to the recognizability of the woman), and
- publication of a photo in which the perpetrator shoots down a passer-by.

Other videos and photos were criticized by the Austrian Press Council, for example, pictures of pools of blood, which many users found distasteful. Still, they did not violate the ethics code. According to the Austrian Press Council, even showing pictures of the assassin and his deeds does not constitute a violation. However, authors criticize these practices as they correspond to the strategies of the perpetrators to disseminate visual material of an attack (Beckett, 2016; Lankford & Madfis, 2018; Marthoz et al., 2017). Moreover, these representations contradict the calls of the police to refrain from publishing footage of the crime for investigative reasons.

In the following, we focus on the discourse surrounding the visual media coverage of the attack and what was criticized for what reasons, who voiced the criticism, and what

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consequences the discourse had. The focus is thus on the discourse about norms of visual communication. The aim is, among other things, to examine the view of users and to contrast it with the view of experts and journalists. This metajournalistic perspective (Carlson, 2016; Franklin, 2014) explores, on the one hand, how the media and journalists themselves cover and understand the role and responsibility of the media when visually reporting on a terrorist attack. In today's networked public spheres (Benkler, 2006), however, metajournalistic discourses are not only represented in journalistic media, nor are they conducted by journalists alone. Other actors from different societal sectors partake, and sites outside the journalistic realm, such as social media platforms, serve as arenas for discussing journalism's issues and norms (Carlson, 2016). The focus of the study is on criticism of journalistic reporting and its use of videos of the attack, as particularly the visual reporting of the two media groups mentioned above triggered an outcry. Due to the strong interconnection of social media communication and journalistic reporting, we consider not only editorial media but also social media users' communications. In the present case, as in numerous other cases, we are confronted with mutual references between media coverage and communication in social media (Authors, 2020). As in this case, 'problematic' images circulating on social media are often published in the media reporting. The journalistic utilization of such contested images can trigger metajournalistic discourses both in news media and on social media platforms. On the latter, users' comments serve as real-time media criticism (Bernhardt & Liebhart, 2019), for example, when users criticize the image-takeover strategies by legacy media or the communication about the attack on the social media platforms themselves. In our networked public spheres, these comments, in turn, can also be taken up by the news media discourses and vice versa (Authors, 2020). What makes the current case so interesting is that the metajournalistic discourse on the visual coverage of the attack has developed mainly because of editorial media's use of images derived from social media.

Method and Research Questions

In the present study, we conducted a qualitative analysis of the discourse on the media's visual coverage of the terrorist attack in Vienna. First, we collected tweets of the Austrian Press Council's account on Twitter chronologically backward. This sampling strategy proved very useful, as the Press Council engaged in a kind of media clipping. We sifted the linked posts and integrated the related media coverage into the material. Additionally, we conducted a keyword search with various combinations of German-language terms (Video*, oe24*, krone*, Twitter*, Facebook*, soziale [social]* Medien [media]*, Attentat [assassination]*, Terror*, Anschlag [attack]*) in the APA-Defacto database, which archives Austrian print and online media. Of the 466 articles found this way, we selected those that dealt with one of the aspects of interest and were not already found in the first step, resulting in a total sample of 214 news articles. The very rich material obtained included journalistic coverage in Austrian daily and weekly newspapers, reports in economic media, on websites of radio and TV broadcasters, and exemplary tweets and social media posts that the media coverage or the Austrian Press Council picked up. We analyzed the material according to the following research questions.

- RQ1: Which actors expressed criticism regarding the reporting?
- RQ2: a) What was criticized about the visual coverage of the terrorist attack and why? b) How were the role of aesthetics and visual modes addressed?
- RQ3: Who is held responsible for what?
- RQ4: In how far is the frame of (self-)censorship applied in the discourse?

The study by Bernhardt and Liebhart (2019) serves as a comparative foil for the analysis. The two authors examined the journalistic discourse surrounding the visual coverage of the attack on the editorial office of the French satirical newspaper Charlie Hebdo in 2015 and the attack on the Christmas market at Berlin's Breitscheidplatz in 2016. Employing a multimodal

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framing analysis, the authors - similar to the interest of the present article - pursued the questions of what, according to the discourse, goes wrong in visual terror reporting, who or what is responsible for it, how this misconduct is to be judged and what should be done differently (Bernhardt & Liebhart, 2019, p. 186).

Since the focus was not on quantifying the material but on mapping the discourse and its formations, we used an iterative procedure during which we examined new material to see if it contained additional argumentations and patterns of interpretation (Keller, 2013; Titscher et al., 2000) until saturation was achieved.

Analysis of the Discourse

Actors Expressing Criticism Regarding the Reporting (RQ1)

In the discourse on the visual coverage of the Vienna terrorist attack, a variety of actors had their say, most of whom were very critical of the coverage of the two media companies, *Mediengruppe Österreich* and *Kronen Zeitung*, as well as of the reporting of rampages and terrorist attacks in general. From the media sector, these were the Austrian Press Council, journalists from other media (some of whom also provided recommendations for ethically acceptable breaking news reporting), the Austrian journalists' union, the Verein Medienjournalismus Österreich (a journalism association), but also journalists, editors-in-chief and publishers of the criticized media (including their apologies). Other participants in the discourse were the regulatory authority KommAustria, advertisers (who temporarily stopped their advertising campaigns in the two mentioned media groups, mainly due to the pressure exerted via social media), politicians (mainly on the topic of press funding), the police (e.g., with recommendations for communication behavior on social media during the rampage), citizens (e.g., with petitions, such as on mein.aufstehn.at as well as with countless complaints on social media and addressed to the Press Council), (communication) scientists (e.g., on the role and responsibility of classical journalism and social media, on press

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promotion or the lack of media education and literacy), psychologists, as well as pedagogues (who mainly addressed the potential consequences for children and measures in the school sector).

Most of the articles and posts appeared within a few hours of the attack. Even while the terrorist activities were still going on, there were numerous recommendations on how users and journalists should behave (especially on Twitter, e.g., in tweets by the police, in handouts for breaking news by journalist and author Ingrid Brodnig, in posts by the Press Council, as well as in recommendations by other users).

We can see that the visual journalistic coverage of the attack was unacceptable for many different actors and thus triggered a broad discourse. This is also evident in the record number of over 1,500 complaints to the Austrian Press Council. This negative record was also the primary reason for the extensive media echo; the problematic photojournalistic reporting itself was often only discussed in the context of these complaints and thus treated as a secondary topic. The titles of many articles illustrate this, e.g., "Over 1,500 complaints about reports on terrorist attack in Vienna" (2020) or "Terror videos in continuous loop: repercussions for oe24.at" (3.11.2020).

However, many users also directly addressed companies advertising in the criticized media via social media. These comments made the companies and brands responsible as 'financiers' of the problematic reporting. Consequently, advertisers also intervened or had to intervene in the discourse, both with statements and by a temporary advertising boycott, stopping their advertising activities in the criticized media.

Even if the occasion is terrible, it is basically to be welcomed that there is such a broad discourse about the appearance of visual reporting and visual user communication in social media. However, it should not be ignored that there were also voices—especially on social media—that stated they could not identify any ethical violations and described the

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public's need for information as a sufficient reason to show pictures of the wounded and dead. However, most actors were critical, especially concerning the journalistic publication of videos and photographs of eyewitnesses. Several media outlets picked up on the results of a representative Gallup poll conducted between 5 and 10 November 2020: A majority of Austrians (58%) were against showing videos and photos of the attack in Austrian media. 36%, on the other hand, were in favor. The survey also asked for agreement on various consequences: 57% agreed with the statement that "companies should not advertise in media that publish such content." 48% agreed that "media that publish such content should not receive press funding in the future." 53% were against the dissemination of officially unconfirmed information by journalists ("Majority opposes publication of assassination videos," 2020).

This leads us directly to the question of what exactly was criticized about the images.

Themes and Reasons in the Criticism of the Visual Coverage of the Terrorist Attack (RQ2a) and the Role of Visual Aesthetics and Visual Modes (RQ2b)

As already mentioned, many different actors participated in the discourse. However, it is remarkable that, in many cases, the criticism was rather unspecific. Bernhardt and Liebhart (2019, pp. 185-186), in their analysis of the discourse in the French and German quality press, found a pronounced awareness of the problem and a high level of reflection on how to deal with terror images. In comparison, the level of reflection in the present material, which, in contrast to the study mentioned above, did not stem solely from quality media, can be classified as lower. If we turn to the statements of the companies that joined the advertising boycott in the criticized media, it is noticeable that the reasons given are very vague. Among the reasons given for the advertising boycott were "outraged reactions" to the reporting. The question remains open: outrage by whom? Another vague justification was "because of the videos." Apparent distancing "from this kind of reporting" was also mentioned, or "the

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distribution of such videos" was described as "impious and distasteful" (Mark, 2020). Other companies justified the advertising ban with "reasons of reverence" (Fidler, 2020a) or with the "imperative of consideration" and "reverence for the victims" ("After terror coverage," 2020). According to the spokesperson for the retail chains Spar, Interspar, and Hervis *Oe24.at* and *Krone.at* showed the videos of the attack, "which is not okay." The mobile phone company Spusu pointed out that it did not want to support "this kind of reporting in any way" (Fidler, 2020a). The actors did not specify what was meant by "this kind" of imagery or reporting. In other words, awareness of the problem was high, but the public reflection on what constituted the problem was limited to a very superficial level.

The journalistic debate on the topic also often showed a very abstract level. On the one hand, for example, in an article in the weekly newspaper *Die Furche*, the contents were briefly outlined: "pools of blood at the crime scene, the shooting of a man, the terrorist aiming at passers-by" (Bayer, 2020). On the other hand, however, there was no detailed problematization. It was criticized that "with such live pictures," media tried to attract more users, that "this kind of reporting" played into the hands of terrorist strategies and that "this form of journalism" was irresponsible (Bayer, 2020). Here, too, image motifs were criticized, but the reasons for the problematization remained mostly unmentioned, and no further explanations were given. This can also be seen in the complaints to the Press Council. Here, too, image content served as the reason for the complaints, but their role, modes of representation, or effects were not further problematized. The complaints related to seven issues: 1) the publication of videos and pictures showing a victim being shot or a police officer being gunned down, 2) the publication of images showing pools of blood at the crime scene, 3) the spreading of rumors and false information, 4) the endangering of the ongoing police operation by uploading video and image material to social media, 5) the publication of images showing fleeing passers-by, 6) publishing identifying reports and images of the

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perpetrator and police officers (including images of the perpetrator posing with weapons) and 7) publishing images of young men (that had nothing to do with the attack) with their upper bodies exposed during police checks ("Over 1,500 complaints about reports of terrorist attack in Vienna," 2020). And again, the picture motives were criticized, but mostly no reasons for the problematization were provided; exceptions were: endangering police operations, misinformation, identification of the perpetrator, and police officers.

From the point of view of visual communication research, this vague criticism can be explained by the fact that although images (can) strongly emotionalize and often trigger strong effects, the verbalization of these impressions and their justifications is very difficult (Authors, 2015). Thus, expertise in analyzing and criticizing the characteristics and impacts of images is needed to evaluate them accordingly—verbally.

"What did the two media do wrong and why?" This question thus remains largely open in the discourse. But we also found some argumentations with a higher level of reflection that goes beyond the assessment of the individual image motif. These more informed arguments can be found primarily in guest editorials by experts, in interviews with academics, or discussions about the actions of the Press Council. In a video interview with the managing director of the Press Council, Alexander Warzilek, *Der Standard* explicitly addressed these questions ("Reporting after the attack," 2020). This interview did not explicitly discuss the case of the attack videos from Vienna, as the examination by the Austrian Press Council was still pending at that time. Instead, Warzilek referred to earlier cases of terror reporting and discussed the central role of images and the ethical challenges. Images are problematic, for example, when the personal interests of the victims (and also their relatives) are violated, and this violation outweighs the informational interest of the general public. A further element of consideration in the criticism of images is that the dissemination of violent images is the terrorists' aim, and their circulation plays into the

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hands of their interests. It is, therefore, necessary to examine the extent to which the media become a tool of the terrorists.

Corinna Milborn, head of information at the private TV channel *Puls-4*, also justified her call on Twitter not to share pictures with the argument that this would serve the goal of the assassin. For this reason, *Puls-4* did not show the videos of the attack and did not mention the name of the killer. Milborn was quoted in numerous reports (e.g., "Journalism ethics," 2020) as saying that this was in line with the editorial guidelines for reporting on IS terror, which were developed together with psychologists and experts on terror and radicalization. The Vienna police also provided reasons on Twitter why videos of the attack should not be shared on social media. The main reason was the danger to civilians and police officers during the police operation, which had not yet been completed. Instead, users were called upon to upload relevant material on a platform provided by the Ministry of the Interior to support the investigative work ("Petition, police, and union," 2020).

Thomas Hofer, editor-in-chief of the industry magazine *Horizont*, adds a central point to the discussion, questioning the informational value of images of atrocities. He asks whether an image was always needed, "as if the mere idea of such an act were not enough." According to Hofer, the news value of depicting victims and of a shooting perpetrator "is close to zero," as it neither serves to clarify nor explain the context but instead stirs up fear and uncertainty and caters to base instincts. "Arguments that media must show comprehensively and relentlessly what is, and that all this can also be seen in the form on social media, do not hold water. Media have a special form of responsibility - especially in such an exceptional situation" (Hofer, 2020).

As these statements show, what was problematic about the reporting, namely the publication of specific images, was put forward very intensively in the discourse. However, as argued above, the *why* remains very vague. Due to the mostly missing reasons for the

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rejection and criticism of the visual coverage, the criticism remained very superficial and abstract. However, for an understanding and negotiation about what kind of reporting is desirable, reasoning it would be essential. Such reasoning was used only by a few experts with high expertise in visual reporting of terrorist attacks and its implications. As a result, the problem awareness in the discourse is very high but remains abstract. The discourse also shows a relatively low level of reflection concerning visual terror coverage. In the discourse, the actors did not address the role of visual aesthetics and visual modes of representation. That is, they completely disregarded the specifics and peculiarities of visual communication and its implications.

Attributions of Responsibility (RQ3)

The situation is similar concerning the central question of media ethics, namely, who bears responsibility for the problematic use of images. While the two media companies were criticized in the shorter contributions directly after the attack, in the course of the discourse, responsibility was explicitly or implicitly attributed to various actors for different reasons.

The following are named as (jointly) responsible institutions or individuals:

- the criticized media companies and their journalists,
- the tabloid journalism in general, which is only interested in quotas,
- the advertising companies that support tabloid journalism or make it possible in the first place,
- politics, as press subsidies disproportionately favor tabloid journalism,
- the users on social media who upload the pictures and videos, search for them out of sensationalism, or share them,
- social media platforms, as they do not fulfill their duty of content moderation, and
- the audiences as a whole, as their voyeurism and sensationalism provided the market for sensationalist reporting in the first place.

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As can be seen from this list, a "distributed responsibility" is suggested here (Floridi, 2016; Funiok, 2005; Schulzke, 2013). Thus, according to the discourse, it is not the publishing houses alone that are to be held responsible, but also a variety of other actors. That means the discourse suggests that the actions of many contribute to the problematic outcome. This network of responsibility makes it difficult to hold individual actors responsible for their actions. In the discourse, particular focus was placed on social media users and platforms. Overall, we can state that on the one hand, actors were named as (co-)responsible whose behavior was problematic in the specific case, i.e., the journalists or the publishing houses of the *Kronen Zeitung* and *oe24*, who showed the pictures and videos. Other actors and institutions were implicitly held responsible because they enabled the landscape and behaviors of tabloid journalism, which have led to the misconduct in reporting the Vienna attack. Named were the politicians who maintain inadequate conditions for press funding (under which large sums go to the tabloids, see below), or the advertising companies, who place advertisements in the criticized tabloid media (see "advertising boycott" below).

Social media users are referred to as responsible parties, as the image and video material from eyewitnesses on the ground was also uploaded to social media platforms and circulated there. Concerning the role of users, the question was often raised as to why they spread violent images via social media in the first place. Experts in the discourse explained this with a particular desire for curiosity and sensational pleasure (Behr et al., 2020; Hausjell, 2020). "People want to do something - but they are often not aware of what is right. This results in ill-considered actions," says psychologist Erna Gappmayer-Löcker. First of all, the sharing is not meant in a toxic way, but users do it rather thoughtlessly. Ingrid Brodnig confirms this: "In the heat of the moment, people pass on what is shocking" (Behr et al., 2020). *The Falter* quotes media scholar Bernhard Pörksen (Goldenberg & Narodslawsky, 2020) concerning the sharing of videos and images. He emphasized the need to invest in

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media education in the current "editorial society." Social media users also have to face ethical questions that used to be left to journalists as gatekeepers. This perspective corresponds to a kind of "renaissance of audience ethics," which emphasizes the role of individualized responsibility in times of produsage (Lischka, 2016).

As far as general media and communication ethics considerations are concerned, we certainly agree with this approach. In any case, there is an urgent need for user ethics and the corresponding promotion of media competence and media education, as is repeatedly demanded in the discourse (Davidovits, 2020; Steinbrenner, 2020; Wolf, 2020). However, the cause of the complaints to the Austrian Press Council was the use of images by two journalistic, editorial media, which showed the images and resorted to amateur footage and a surveillance video. As stated above, a significant challenge of live reporting is verifying image material that reaches the editorial offices from different sources. Just because footage exists and circulates in other contexts does not mean that editorial media can or should use it.

Communication scientist Josef Trappel, who spoke out several times in the discourse, seconds this line of argumentation. He emphasized that it is precisely when editorial media believe they have to compete with social media platforms that it becomes problematic. The mission of quality media is instead to reflect critically and not succumb to the dictate of "speed before quality." In critical situations, such as the Vienna night of terror, restraint should be the order of the day. "Journalistic media have a classification function. They should only publish information if it is ensured that it is true," said Trappel. Also, the argument that the content is "already out there anyway" on social media is wrong: "The idea that you have to be equally quick is a misconception" (Behrsabrina Glas, 2020, p. 21). Elsewhere, he formulated his criticism even more clearly and separated the responsibility that social media users and platforms bear from that of journalists: "Anyone who does not understand that the digital platforms Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, WhatsApp, Telegram, and whatever they are

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all called, follow a fundamentally different logic than editorial media must be considered an editorial endangerer" (Trappel, 2020). He added that some of the editorial media have learned nothing from the past and continuously ignore any responsibility and distribute the videos for the sake of clickbait.

We also want to point out that many social media users asked others not to share the videos and images and even employed counter-strategies to prevent circulation or make it difficult to find the footage. For example, one counter-tactic was to use the Twitter hashtag #0211w (which was used for posts on the Vienna terror attack) to share cat pictures. In this way, the users aimed to hijack the visual discourse and push the videos of violence further down the timeline or make them more challenging to find within a barrage of cat pictures. This strategy was already successfully used on Twitter during the security lockdown following the attack in Brussels in November 2015 (Jensen et al., 2020). In addition, flagging and blocking requests were called for on social media platforms.

Furthermore, various tweets and posts also addressed the responsibility of the companies that placed ads in the outlets of *Mediengruppe Österreich* and *Kronen Zeitung*. The companies, in turn, reacted with an advertising boycott. Many social media users spoke out critically, and it can be assumed that they were significantly involved in the advertising boycott of many companies. For example, a call for a boycott on Twitter listed and directly addressed companies that placed advertisements in the media in question. Several companies (such as Billa and Hofer) responded to this call with tweets and announced that they would have stopped placing advertisements in the respective media ("After terror coverage," 2020). Requests to the companies came from users and activists on Twitter. Some companies stopped their advertisements in the media groups' online outlets; others stopped both the placements on the digital platforms and in the print products of *Mediengruppe Österreich* and *Kronen Zeitung*.

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In many cases, the boycott was only temporary; a longer-term boycott was announced in fewer cases. Advertising agency head Kapfer characterized this boycott as a necessary "lever to bring about change" in the tabloid media ("Terror reporting," 2020). But the boycott itself was also presented as a media ethical dilemma. Thus, media ethics issues are raised when companies pressure publishing houses to change their editorial practices (even if in this case, it means pressure to comply with the code of ethics for the Austrian press). Company spokespersons took up this problem in their justifications of the boycott or its later lifting and described their (often short-living) boycott as an essential signal (Mark, 2020). It is also undeniable that there is a sensitive, economic interdependency between the advertising companies and the media, which strongly limits the scope for boycotts. As the users' criticism of the companies and the attribution of co-responsibility shows, unethical journalism is also a problem for brand safety because it does not provide an adequate editorial framework for advertising, i.e., it is not a trustworthy environment ("Digital industry association iab criticizes 'unscrupulous disaster journalism' after terrorist attack," 2020).

In addition to social media users, responsibility was also implicitly attributed to the general audience. It has been argued that users increase the reach of sensationalist media through their interest in sensationalist content. However, this implicit attribution of responsibility was accompanied by an appeal to editorial media not to give in to this audience interest. The president of the Association of Austrian Newspapers, Markus Mair, for example, spoke of the high responsibility that journalistic media had in such incidents. And this responsibility, according to him, was not compatible with optimizing market shares and striving for higher ratings. Mair stressed that the overriding principle of media must be to be closest to the truth and not to compete with social media (Behr, 2020). In the daily *Oberösterreichische Nachrichten*, *oe24* and *krone.at* were criticized for "serving voyeurism

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[to] increase market shares and [neglecting] respect, victim protection, and empathy" (Grubmüller, 2020).

The same pattern of argumentation can be found in the justifications of some media and journalists for not showing the footage in question (such as Corinna Milborn, head of information at the private television station *Puls 24*; Eva Dichand, editor of the free and wide-reaching Vienna-based tabloid newspaper *heute*; Clemens Oistic, online editor-in-chief of the same paper). In their statements, they explicitly distanced themselves from tabloid journalism in the style of *Kronen Zeitung* and *oe24*. For example, Dichand tweeted, "we are different" ("Terror videos in continuous loop," 2020). Journalists from other media thus blamed the 'bad style' tabloid journalism with its mechanisms oriented towards sensationalism and quotas. Implicitly, however, they also blamed the readers, as, without readers who demand this kind of reporting, there would be no economic market for these media. Clemens Oistic expressed the implicit co-responsibility of the recipients particularly clearly. He tweeted on November 3 that the videos were not shown in the online edition of *heute* because, while the situation was still unclear, they did not want to endanger human lives, even if they would lose a lot of users. The news magazine *Profil* quotes Oistic's tweet stating, "yes, we gave the competition a chunk of clicks. But do we want to risk human lives for a few hundred thousand clicks? I think that is shabby" (Paterno, 2020).

Social media platforms, such as *Facebook*, were also held responsible in the discourse. It is voiced that *Facebook* even facilitated the dissemination of violent videos and images instead of preventing it. A *Facebook* spokesperson not only expressed "shock at the events in Vienna" but also promised that the company would remove the videos from its Facebook and Instagram platforms (Pichler & Sulzbacher, 2020). In this context, e.g., the national quality dailies *Die Presse* and *Der Standard* pointed out that *Facebook* often has had problems removing such content and reminded of the video of the Christchurch perpetrator of

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2019, which was uploaded again and again. Here, the media again addressed the responsibility of users (Steinbrenner, 2020). In this context, data protection expert Wolfie Christl (Pichler & Sulzbacher, 2020) and digital expert Ingrid Brodnig (Behr et al., 2020) pointed out the problematic nature of the *Facebook* tool Crisis-Response. For example, in tweets quoted by the *Standard* (Pichler & Sulzbacher, 2020), Christl argues that this tool not only made it possible to mark oneself as "safe" but also to upload said videos. He accused *Facebook* of "gross irresponsibility." Not only did videos showing the perpetrator shooting a passer-by end up in users' timelines, but they were also played automatically. Christl criticized this and that, although *Facebook* later took action against the uploads, the videos were sometimes only hidden behind a warning message announcing that they might show violence. In addition, even small changes, such as the insertion of texts or overlays, would lead to the automated system to no longer recognizing the videos and the control process, which begins with the reporting of the video by the users, having to be restarted.

Directly following on from this, political actors were named as co-responsible. In an interview with the news magazine *News*, communication scientist Fritz Hausjell discussed legal issues and platform regulation. At the European level, it had been missed to "impose binding legal foundations for the American platforms in time" (Edhofer, 2020).

Several journalists, as well as the media spokespersons of the opposition parties SPÖ and Neos and the governing party Greens, spoke out in favor of a reform of state media subsidies according to quality criteria (Bayer, 2020; "Call for different press funding," 2020). In this context, they referred to the imbalance in direct press funding between tabloid and quality newspapers. Due to the "watering-can principle" (which describes the principle of giving everyone an equal share of the subsidy, without examining the actual needs) in the distribution of state press subsidy funds, which is calculated based on the print run instead of quality criteria, tabloids benefit greatly. As had been discussed for many years, reforms are

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needed (Bayer, 2020). Therefore, the debate about the publication of the attack videos became a starting point to revive these discussions. Various academics spoke out, demanding, among other things, that funding be provided according to qualitative criteria and with more transparency and that the financing of new digital formats be integrated. For example, Fritz Hausjell argued that it was high time: "For years we have seen a strengthening of the already dominant media instead of promoting media diversity" (Bayer, 2020, p. 20). And journalists and the journalists' union also appealed to the federal government to distribute subsidies and public funds based on journalistic ethics and quality criteria: "Like the journalists themselves, it [the government] also bears responsibility for this decisive pillar of a democracy" (Grubmüller, 2020). In addition to the co-responsibility due to the direct means of press and media funding, politics was also repeatedly criticized for government advertisements as a form of indirect press funding (Bayer, 2020). Political actors and parties should withdraw these funds from media that behave unethically. The communication scientist Christopher Buschow suggested to "abolish government advertisements and transfer the financial resources to a transparent funding initiative" (Fidler, 2020b).

And an online petition organized by civil society, which called for a reorganization of media support and registered almost 80,000 signatures as of the end of November 2020, also demanded a reform of the legal regulation of media funding. "State media funding should be linked even more strongly to fundamental, ethical and moral quality criteria," the petition is quoted by the *Kleine Zeitung* ("Petition, police, and union," 2020).

The Frame of (Self-)Censorship in the Discourse RQ4)

Interestingly, in the debates in the editorial media, the actors did not relate the journalistic usage or non-usage of the images to censorship or self-censorship. We did not find a single statement in which not showing or showing the images was addressed with arguments of censorship or self-censorship. As outlined above, a few actors – especially on

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social media – publicly advocated showing the videos and images, arguing that the press had a duty to inform the public. However, they did not use an argumentative reference to (self-)censorship if the media would not show these images.

Conclusion

Once again, the analysis of the discourse on the terrorist attack in Vienna confirms that criticizing images is not easy. Often the criticism is limited to a vague feeling towards the content of the image. The viewers are convinced: 'this pictorial representation is not acceptable.' But it is difficult to give reasons for this, to explain why the picture is unacceptable. Image criticism or analytical engagement with the image and its modes of representation is far from trivial. Image competencies are required to verbalize how the visual communicates and 'works.' In the example analyzed, this is very clear: a variety of actors speak out and criticize that *Mediengruppe Österreich* and *Kronen Zeitung* showed indecent images that violate journalistic codes. There is a broad consensus that this was an improper image usage in a journalistic context. However, the level of reflection remains relatively low; hardly any reasons are given why 'this kind of reporting' or 'these images' are unacceptable. Moreover, the discussion throughout the coverage is limited to image motives. Image aesthetics and modes of representation are not discussed at all. *How* something is shown is thus excluded.

Visual communication research is called upon to contribute here explicitly and argue why specific images and particular aesthetics are to be criticized, not only concerning terror reporting but also in general. This is particularly important because images spread remarkably quickly. Therefore, as Hausjell (2020) criticized on a meta-level, it is necessary to adjust general norms and standards. Otherwise, the same thing would happen again in each new case. The aspect of time pressure and speed (Beuthner, 2003; Bernhardt & Liebhart, 2019; Riegert & Olsson, 2007) was explicitly mentioned by several actors, such as Josef

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Trappel (Behrsabrina Glas, 2020) or Ingrid Brodnig ("Petition, police, and union," 2020). While Trappel refers to the journalistic use of images, Brodnig refers to sharing images in social media.

An ethical approach to images can therefore not only be expected from journalism, but users can also be held responsible, for example, by reflecting on the potential consequences and implications of the use of images. This refers both to users as the audience of journalism, whose sensationalism and voyeurism are repeatedly put forward as arguments for the use of visual material, and to users in social media who upload, share, like, or simply view this content. It can also be read as an appeal to academia, and visual communication research, in particular, to help shape the discourse in the sense of the third mission. By no means is it meant that users are understood as a homogeneous mass that can be saved from harmful image content through education. On the one hand, the thousands of complaints from users to the Austrian Press Council show how sensitive large parts of the population are to such content. On the other hand, research into the effects of images shows how complex the effects of image content are.

In addition, we think it is imperative to assess the responsibility for certain visual practices in the respective contexts. In other words, it is not helpful, in the sense of shared responsibility, to name all actors who are somehow in contact with the respective context (here, journalistic image reporting on terror topics in tabloid media) as directly responsible. This can and should be a second step. The first step is to measure journalistic practice and the use of images against the standards that are applied to journalism. Only in the next stage of exploring responsibilities it becomes relevant who co-finances this journalism, demands it, or puts it under competitive pressure. If many actors are held responsible in the sense of shared responsibility, it is more difficult to name the main culprit(s) and focus on unacceptable practices. On the other hand, shared responsibility - in a second step - also makes it possible

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to bring about changes by putting pressure on those who are jointly responsible, be it advertisers, politicians, or users.

In both steps, processes of change can be set in motion. As norms regarding visual communication are communicatively constructed (Venema, 2019), this mutual reference of the various co-responsible parties can drive the "updating" of norms, as called for by Hausjell (2020).

As already mentioned, the voice of experts on visual communication and photojournalism would have been essential in the discourse. Bernhardt and Liebhart (2019, p. 194) found in their analysis of the discourse on Charlie Hebdo that expert knowledge "is the exception concerning visuals and their specific impact potentials." The authors highlighted this as a remarkable result, as the contributions particularly emphasized the problematic nature of visuals in news coverage. We make similar observations for the case of the terrorist attack in Vienna. The use of images in media coverage and its violation of fundamental ethical principles were the explicit starting point of the debate and discourse on the norms and values of images in reporting terrorist acts. Therefore, in this case, numerous experts from academia and journalistic and legal fields had their say.

On the one hand, this was very important for the discourse's level of reflection, which was otherwise characterized by a vague verbalization of the problems. However, the voice of visual communication researchers was largely missing. Journalistic principles were discussed in detail, but not the peculiarities of visual communication and its implications. This is shown by the fact that the role of aesthetics and visual modes of representation was wholly left out, i.e., the question of how and with which mechanisms terror images unfold their effects.

Finally, we would like to make a practical recommendation for journalists, which can also apply to social media users. Often – remind the keyword "speed" – people do not reflect sufficiently on the material before using images, but this reflection on images is a prerequisite

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for ethical, responsible use of images. If one is faced with the question, "How should images be used?" one can be guided by the following two principles: 1. Not everything needs to be illustrated. The incredible power of pictures to quickly convey many details and show human emotions can also be a disadvantage. Often it is enough to say something abstractly-verbally. As Carina Milborn, the head of information at the private TV channel *Puls-4*, and the mentioned recommendations (Beckett, 2016; Marthoz et al., 2017) on responsible reporting on terrorist attacks or Lankford and Madfis (2018) have put it concerning mass killers, "don't name them, don't show them," thus denying them the attention they seek. 2. Select images according to appropriate selection standards. Even if these still have to be established for many contexts, they are already well defined in journalism by professional standards. This is one of the reasons why a canon of images or image types that are typically used has already been established for terror reporting; we found these also in the analyzed case. Media used mainly images of barriers and heavily armed police, emergency forces or blue lights without context, police in action (during the attack), candles and flowers at the memorial site, roses in bullet holes, and candles in close-up (after the terrorist act). Indeed, as can be seen from this list, these are not very concrete images having relatively low emotionalizing potential, as they do not show the suffering of victims. But this again illustrates guiding principle 1: Not everything needs visualization!

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